

IMPACT ANALYSIS OF DIGITAL LIBRARY ON USERS OF COLLEGES AND UNIVERSITIES IN WEST BENGAL (INDIA)**Dr.Arun Modak ¹, Moumita Pari ²,**

¹Research Guide, Dept. of Library & Info.Science
Sri Satya Sai University of Technology and Medical Sciences,
Sehore Bhopal-Indore Road, Madhya Pradesh, India.

¹Research Scholar, Dept. of Library & Info.Science
Sri Satya Sai University of Technology and Medical Sciences,
Sehore Bhopal-Indore Road, Madhya Pradesh, India.

Abstract

An educational facility that provides students with post-secondary education programmes that last either three or four years and culminate in the awarding of a bachelor's degree is typically referred to as an institution of higher learning (also known as a college library). These programmes can last anywhere from one to four years. In addition to the traditional services that it offers, the library also provides new services such as automated circulation, web-OPAC, access to electronic resources 24 hours a day from home, an e-CAS facility, and so on. These new services are in addition to the traditional services that it offers. This is done to bring library services into line with the contemporary period and to fulfil the ever-increasing demand placed on libraries by users in the modern day. There are four separate types of individuals that make up every given library: professional, semi-professional, non-professional, and technical staff. In general, there are four distinct kinds of personnel that make up each particular library. 16 of the country's 42 general education colleges that are either government-run or government-aided were chosen to participate in the study, and 15 of those colleges supplied responses to the questionnaire. The institutions of higher education that took part in our study include three general degree colleges that are operated by the government and twelve general degree colleges that get financial assistance from the government. The survey approach is being utilised to carry out this inquiry, and a questionnaire has been dispatched to each of the educational institutions. The findings of the survey are analysed, and a conclusion is reached through the presentation of the results as well as some recommendations regarding the scope of potential future research in this area.

Keywords Library services, Staff formula, College libraries.

Introduction

Libraries are not falling behind the times in the same way that information and communications technology (ICT) is expanding into all facets of our lives and activities to make the work easier and more efficient. If we want to be in a position to offer useful services to the people who visit our library, it is absolutely necessary for us to have a properly staffed facility that is also stocked with an adequate amount of materials. In addition to the traditional services that it offers, the library also provides new services such as automated circulation, web-OPAC, access to electronic resources 24 hours a day from home, an e-CAS facility, and so on. These new

services are in addition to the traditional services that it offers. This is done to bring library services into line with the contemporary period and to fulfil the ever-increasing demand placed on libraries by users in the modern day. Users who frequent academic libraries, such as those found in general degree colleges, often include members of both the student body and the teaching staff of the respective educational institutions. As a result, the quantity of personnel required is decided by the number of collections, the number of users, and the diverse requirements of the users, among other factors. Both the students' socioeconomic position and the environment in which they live have an effect on the kind of information that the children require in their daily lives. This study makes an effort to present a full picture of the undergraduate colleges that are a part of West Bengal State University by performing a survey in each of the libraries that are located on each of the individual college campuses.

RELATED WORK

Sushanta Banerjee et al(2021) Over the course of the past ten years, there has been a significant movement in the direction of digital libraries in Indian libraries. On the other hand, the management of digital libraries is not the same as that of traditional libraries. With the help of this survey, an effort was made to gain a better understanding of the current state of the administration of digital libraries at the educational institutions located within the state of West Bengal. The primary emphasis of the research was placed on the management of digital resources in addition to conventional resource types. The need for traditional library resources as opposed to digital library resources among the student bodies of these universities was another primary topic of the survey. Through the use of questionnaires and interviews, data was gathered from ten different colleges located within the Indian state of West Bengal. Several other statistical measures, including the coefficient of variation, were used in the analysis of the data that was obtained. According to the findings of the survey, even if educational institutions have begun allocating funds toward digital resources, there is still a significant appetite among student communities for traditional materials. It was also noticed that the speed of the internet is not sufficient for the appropriate utilisation of the resources, and that there is an immediate need for training for both the employees of the library and the users of digital resources.

Rohtash Singh and Sudhir Tyagi et al(2018) According to this law of library science, libraries needed to go forward in a way that made sense, and information and communications technology (ICT) provided the requisite energy while automatization finished the process of document management by employing classification schemes. Even though fully automated classification won't be possible for quite some time yet, recent developments in a variety of database systems that are used by libraries demonstrate an innovative approach to the classification of library works that incorporates online resources. In this day and age, even though fully automated classification won't be possible for quite some time yet. To utilise any of the online tools that are discussed in this post, you will not need to provide any kind of login credentials. If you find yourself in a difficult scenario, use the internet resources that have been described above as a guide, and compare the results that they reach to the classification method that was originally used.

Lanagan, J. (2012) People's interactions with technology are through a period of fast change, during which they are becoming increasingly mobile, social, and multimedia-based. When it comes to the production of content, mobile social applications that are utilised by a significant number of persons present a challenge to traditional methods of information production and dissemination. Since the beginning of time, libraries have played the role as storage facilities for the information content of societies. In this capacity, they have acted as a permanent record of the aspects of a civilisation that ought to be remembered. It is difficult for libraries of today to fulfil this function because of the nature and utility of mobile, social, and multimedia content. This alters the type of information we seek to curate and keep, which makes it challenging for libraries to fulfil this function. The more static models of information that are used in digital libraries are being challenged by the information that is more organic and dynamic. This article provides a description of two digital library systems that archive video footage from the sports domain and allow users to annotate and blend information from many sources. Both of these digital library systems can be found here. We demonstrate how the typical function of a (digital) library can be enlarged by using study of how it is currently being implemented.

Witten, et al(2009) Training in digital librarianship is required for anyone seeking employment in digital libraries. The selection of digital materials, their purchase, their organisation, their accessibility, and their preservation are all tasks that fall under the purview of a digital librarian. Planning, implementing, and maintaining digital services are all essential tasks. However, there are now only a limited number of training opportunities available for librarians despite the fact that digital libraries call for new positions and responsibilities. The Institute on Digital Library Development at the University of California (UC) Berkeley Library was able to be funded thanks to a grant awarded by the Department of Education. This money was intended to meet the requirements for retraining. Workers at libraries, museums, and archives were given training by the Institute on how to address challenges posed by digital libraries. At the Institute, some of the most important lessons focused on digital library theory and practise, HyperText Markup Language (HTML), imaging, optical character recognition, access and indexing, resource selection for digitization, and effective training methods. The majority of the required reading and other materials for the class are available on the internet.

Esse, et al.(2014) Academic programming aimed at teaching library users how to get the most out of their visits to the institution's resources and services is known as user education. There's nothing more stunning than thinking that universities are nothing more than libraries that have been surrounded by other structures. As far as user education and library utilisation are concerned, there is still a long way to go. In libraries around the world, there are numerous hurdles to overcome, all of which have an impact on how effectively available resources are put to use by library users. An investigation into the impact of a library education programme on undergraduate students in Nigeria's southern area is the goal of this study. Questions such as how librarians have organised the library so that students can best utilise its resources are addressed. Is library users adequately and meaningfully instructed? However, despite the existence of user education programmes, and despite the fact that users believe these

programmes increased their library use, the library must continue its efforts to educate library users by creating more means of user education. The majority of library patrons say that user education programmes have increased their attendance at the institution.

DIGITAL LIBRARY ON USERS OF COLLEGES AND UNIVERSITIES IN WEST BENGAL (INDIA)

College libraries serve an extremely important purpose in the education and research processes of the institution by collecting and distributing information. Students' entire development is aided by the availability of instructional data and knowledge to them through digital libraries, in addition to traditional ones, which contributes to their overall growth. In digital libraries, students can access a wide variety of resources by using a single user interface to navigate the library's contents. It is possible to access databases from any location, which is one of the primary factors contributing to its meteoric surge in popularity. In light of all of these potential benefits, it was decided to conduct research into the current state of digital library services in the educational institutions of West Bengal. The author visited more than a dozen different schools in order to gather information for a study she was conducting on the state of digital libraries in undergraduate schools in the state of West Bengal. It was decided to conduct a poll in order to get accurate feedback from many individuals, including college presidents and librarians. Whether or not the library services are automated, the number of volumes that the library owns, the number of periodicals that it subscribes to, the number of students and teachers who use the library on a regular basis, and the amount of students and teachers who use the library on a regular basis are all things that we would like to know. What kinds of electronic resources does the library subscribe to that patrons can access? How strong of a demand is there for electronic books, specifically? Which one, traditional resources or online ones, do people turn to more frequently? The annual budgets for traditional resources and those for online resources are distinct. How well-trained the staff members of the library are to manage digital resources is an important consideration. The volume of books and magazines that are subscribed to by libraries is almost always the same throughout all educational institutions, notwithstanding factors such as the age of the college, the size of the college library, and the number of students that are enrolled. In general, most libraries have a collection of between 13,000 and 18,000 volumes and subscribe to seven to eight magazines through the INFLIBNET service. Additionally, most libraries offer computer access to its patrons. The average annual expenditure on books and periodicals by colleges is between Rs. 70,000 and Rs. 80,000, with an additional Rs. 5,900 being spent on online resources. As a consequence of this, four of the school's principals claimed that the allocation of funds for the purchase of books and online resources is contingent on the sum that is received from the state government. One of the school's principals stated that the institution spends approximately Rs. 3,000,000 on new books each year. After conducting interviews with college librarians, it was discovered that a significant number of librarians believe library automation to be synonymous with digitization of the library. When questioned about the automation technologies they use, the responses frequently confirm the author's conflicted feelings about the topic. Others have stated that they make use of proprietary software that has been modified to meet their particular requirements,

while others have stated that they make use of software such as KOHA to assist them in automating their services. It would appear that the services provided by certain libraries are completely computerised, but other libraries say that only a fraction of their activities are fully computerised. The conversation about internet download speeds elicited a range of responses from the librarians. When asked about the speed of the internet, some people thought it was quick, while others said it was slow. The librarians were also presented with a query regarding access to the library's electronic resources remotely. It was observed that not a single library offers faculty and students access to the internet remotely. Through a series of interviews with college presidents and librarians, a comparison of the utility of traditional resources with electronic ones was conducted. Surprisingly, all of the librarians agree that the traditional resource is considered to be more popular than the electronic resources. The majority of librarians who replied to a study asking why conventional resources continue to be more popular than electronic ones claimed that the lack of customers' experience with how to efficiently use electronic resources is the primary factor in explaining this phenomenon. College presidents feel that librarians should take the initiative to promote e-resources through user education programmes rather than waiting for librarians to promote e-resources through user education programmes. It is recommended that a user orientation programme on electronic resources be considered in order to encourage people to make use of these resources. It is also really interesting to hear what they have to say regarding how quickly the internet operates. According to the responses of the vast majority of people interviewed, the speed of the internet does not play a role in the distribution or utilisation of online resources. It is generally accepted that a low level of awareness is the key factor contributing to low utilisation. Despite the fact that many educational institutions have access to online resources, very few of them are actually being utilised. Then there's the problem of organising all of the online resources in a way that's manageable. The administration of electronic resources in an approachable manner is of the utmost importance. Librarians need to obtain sufficient training in order to successfully manage and disseminate the contents they are responsible for. They should be encouraged to participate in educational activities that will help them develop. This will be beneficial to everyone involved. The management of these databases ought to be handled by librarians who are able to demonstrate their expertise to users of the service. A large part of encouraging librarians to make use of electronic resources is in the hands of college administrators. In order to make a comparison between traditional resources and e-resources, we employ a statistical tool called a pie chart.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

The purpose of this study is to gather information about the current status and condition of the library staff, as well as the services they provide to their clients, in the West Bengal State University's college libraries. It is the goal of the study to provide a state-of-the-art report based on the data gathered from the survey in order to determine the current status of library staff structure, collections of resources, and services.

METHODOLOGY

Two of the colleges analysed had fewer than 10,000 volumes, the bulk of the colleges studied had between 10,000 and 20,000 volumes, and two of the institutions studied had more than 50,000 volumes. Six of the colleges that were polled had a combined enrollment of over 2,000 students.

One college offers students access to a book bank, three colleges offer students reprographic services, four colleges offer students access to CAS, and one college offers students access to a newspaper clippings service.

Within the college libraries that were studied, there were only six library orientation programmes, three lecture and workshop programmes, and six book fairs or exhibitions.

The N-List programme is made available electronically as a resource by the vast majority of academic libraries. 14 of the 15 universities utilise Koha as the automation software for their libraries, while the other college utilises SOUL.

The Dspace digital library software is used for one of the Institutional Repositories at one of the 15 colleges that were researched.

Six of the 15 colleges have wireless internet access throughout their libraries, while all of the institutions' libraries have internet connectivity. The common areas and services provided to library patrons, as well as the vast majority of college libraries, are watched over by CCTV.

- OPAC facilities are offered in each of the 15 college libraries, making it simple for customers to locate the resources they require.

- There is a dearth of skilled staff to deliver services in a timely and effective manner in this location. There are four colleges that provide Web OPAC facilities, which enable patrons to conduct catalogue searches from the convenience of their own homes or any other location.

The fact that library employees are un

able to use new technology because of incompatibilities presents a significant barrier to the introduction of new services.

The absence of financial assistance often places limitations on the resources and equipment available in libraries.

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

One can get a good idea of the situations and conditions of the college libraries that are administered by the West Bengal University by reading this study. The study includes a SWOC analysis of the staff structure, collections, user strength, traditional as well as modernised services that are provided by the libraries. The purpose of the survey is to gain first-hand knowledge about the operations of college libraries as well as suggestions for further development. This is done so that many of the new services that are becoming available in this age of information and communications technology can be provided by these libraries, and so that libraries can play a significant role both now and in the future. In the past ten years, there has been a significant shift toward digitization in Indian libraries. Taking this fact into consideration, an effort was made to assess the library services provided in colleges located in the state of West Bengal. During the course of the field study as well as after it was completed,

it was discovered that the process of digitization has an extremely minimal effect on the operation of college libraries. The vast majority of educational institutions do not own any kind of infrastructure for digital resources. It is fascinating to see that the demand for traditional resources is significantly higher in comparison to the demand for digital resources. Students from a select number of educational institutions admitted that they know nothing about digital resources. Therefore, it is essential that the librarians of the colleges make more of an effort to aggressively market the digital resources that are available at their individual universities. It is vitally crucial to raise people's awareness about the resources available online. The administrative heads of educational institutions ought to encourage their institutions' librarians to promote digital resources. The necessary infrastructure for managing this significant resource ought to be present in educational institutions. Connectivity to a lightning-fast internet service is one of the most important aspects of digital resources. It has come to our attention that a number of educational institutions do not provide enough connectivity to the internet at fast speeds. It is up to the administration of the college to ensure that there is adequate internet connectivity in order to make this service possible. Because we now live in the age of digital resources, it is impossible for librarians to disregard this significant resource when providing their services. It is therefore advised that librarians should give equal significance in marketing both traditional and digital resources with the assistance of college authorities. This would be done with the hope that more people would utilise both types of resources.

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